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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

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БОЖХОНА ОРГАНИ ХОДИМЛАРИ ТОМОНИДАН ГИЁҲВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРИНИ КОНТРАБАНДАСИНИ АНИҚЛАШДА ПРОФАЙЛИНГДАН ФойДАЛАНИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада божхона органлари ходимларининг касбий фаолиятида профайлинг технологияларидан фойдаланиш имкониятлари ва натижалари таҳлил қилинган. Қўлланиладиган психологик технологиялар тизими сифатида профайлиннинг функционал мазмуни очиб берилган, бу потенциал ҳуқуқбузарни аниқлаш ва унинг хулқ-атвор тенденцияларини башорат қилиш имконини беради. Божхона ходимларининг экспресс диагностикасининг айрим хусусиятлари келтирилган. Ўз малакаси ва касбий маҳоратини ошириш учун божхона ходимларига нафақат касбий билим, балки мулоқот кўникмаларини ривожлантириш, мантиқий фикрлаш қобилияти, турли хил психологик кўникмалар, хусусиятлар ва усулларга эга бўлиш зарур.

Калит сўзлар: божхона ходимлари, профайлинг технологияси, экспресс диагностика, профиллаш, малака, психологик профил, кузатиш.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОФАЙЛИНГА ПРИ ВЫЯВЛЕНИИ КОНТРАБАНДЫ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ СОТРУДНИКАМИ ТАМОЖЕННЫХ ОРГАНОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируются возможности и результаты применения технологий профайлинга в профессиональной деятельности должностных лиц таможенных органов. Раскрывается функциональное содержание профайлинга как системы прикладных психологических технологий, позволяющих определить потенциального правонарушителя и дать прогноз его поведенческим тенденциям. Приведены некоторые особенности проведения экспресс-диагностики сотрудников таможенных органов. Сотрудники таможенных органов для совершенствования своей компетентности и профессионализма необходимы не только профессиональные знания, но и развитие навыков общения, способности логически мыслить, владение разнообразными психологическими умениями, свойствами, приемами.

Ключевые слова: сотрудники таможенных органов, технология профайлинга, экспресс-диагностика, профилирование, компетентность, психологический профиль, наблюдение.

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PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF PROFILING WHEN DETECTING SMUGGLING DRUGS BY CUSTOMS OFFICIALS

ANNOTATION

The article analyzes the possibilities and results of using profiling technologies in the professional activities of customs officials. The functional content of profiling as a system of applied psychological technologies is revealed, which makes it possible to identify a potential offender and predict his behavioral tendencies. Some features of the express diagnostics of customs officials are given. To improve their competence and professionalism, customs officers need not only professional knowledge, but also the development of communication skills, the ability to think logically, possession of a variety of psychological skills, properties, and techniques.

Keywords: customs officials, profiling technologies, express diagnostics, profiling, competence, psychological profile, observation.

Currently, officials of the customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan solve a number of important tasks in the implementation of customs control at checkpoints on the customs borders of the state: suppression of smuggling of drugs, explosives, weapons, ammunition, tobacco products and other illegally moved items.

In carrying out these activities, Customs Officials (COs) have to deal directly with persons who are trying to smuggle these goods in vehicles, personal luggage, carry-on luggage, clothing, on the body, and even inside the body.

To detect illegally moved goods, various technical means of customs control are successfully used - X-ray installations for examining luggage and goods, metal detectors, scanners for personal screening of a person.

For this purpose, trained search service dogs are also used by cynologists. Profiling can also provide great assistance to customs officials. The work practice of customs inspectors during customs control is traditionally based on individual contact with carriers and is a communicative process.

Currently, profiling technology is already being used in major airports of the world along with the use of modern technical means of screening passengers, their hand luggage and luggage.

The use of profiling technologies allows, based on an analysis of the characteristics of a person's appearance, signs of his verbal and non-verbal behavior, to determine ("read") a potential offender, which, of course, contributes to a more efficient performance of job duties, since its methods help make a psychological portrait of a person [1].

Profiling (from the English word "profile" - profile) is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities used in different areas of life [2].

The main purpose of profiling is to identify potentially dangerous persons, and its basis is a visual diagnosis of a person's psycho-emotional state (observation and a special survey, fixing psychological behavioral reactions in responses - non-verbal and verbal).

The idea of the possibility of recreating the mental and physical appearance of a person based on the traces left by him at the scene appeared quite a long time ago. However, it was only in the 1950s that the first experience of using psychological profiling as a forensic tool to search for an unknown criminal took place.

Profiling is a new direction in psychological science that has appeared relatively recently and allows deciphering non-verbal and verbal components used in interpersonal communication.

According to experts, profiling makes it possible to obtain the most objective information about the potential danger of the subject and can be effectively used for preventive measures to prevent terrorist attacks in transport and crowded places, as well as in other areas of official activity of employees of internal affairs bodies.

Profiling is considered as a technology for assessing and predicting human behavior based on such characteristics as: manifestations of the autonomic nervous system, emotional states, speech features, non-verbal manifestations, appearance features and other informative signs.

In the 1970s, Special Agent Howard Teten showed interest in investigating the investigation in Brussels. Thetan began to use Brassell's work on building a psychological profile to explain criminal behavior.

At first, this initiative rested solely on the enthusiasm of specific people; there was no special organization for such work. However, already in 1984, the National Center for the Study of Violent Crimes was formed, just from that moment on, the method of psychological profiling received official recognition.

The main tasks of the National Center were to identify, identify and search for criminals who committed serial murders and especially serious crimes against a person. To accumulate and systematize information on this category of cases in the United States, a single national computer system allows, if necessary, to quickly extract the necessary data on specific solved and unsolved crimes [3].

As well as the method of psychological profiling, it was actively used in the investigation of multi-episode murders committed with extreme cruelty in the FBI Behavioral Sciences Unit, BSU (Behavioral Sciences Division of the FBI Academy) Quantico, Virginia.

To date, the method of psychological profiling is widely used at the stage of preliminary investigation in many countries of Europe and America, many employees are trained at the FBI Academy in Quantico, where back in the 70s a special training course was created dedicated to the science of the possible behavior of a criminal.

Among the European countries that have adopted this technique, we will cite the Federal Republic of Germany as an example. In the structure of the criminal police, departments have been created where police officers who have undergone special training in forming the psychological profile of a criminal that meets accepted standards conduct professional activities. These employees have a legal education, as well as practical experience in solving crimes.

The process of activity of such police officers is called Operational Crime Analysis (OFA). These structural units are created at two levels: the level of the Federal Office of the Criminal Police of Germany and the level of the departments of the criminal police of the lands) [4].

Identification of behavioral signs of individuals with destructive intentions in crowded places (airports, train stations, metro, educational institutions, theaters, large shopping centers, discos, clubs, etc.) and timely localization of a potential source of conflict is the main content of the work of profilers, working in public places. This technology has been used for many years by the Israeli airline El Al, one of the safest in the world. In 1968, her employees developed this method of combating terrorism. In the United States, there are also profiling programs that search for and accumulate statistical data on suspicious behavior patterns [5].

The Israeli concept of profiling is based on the premise that every passenger can be a terrorist, and every item can be an explosive device. Therefore, all activities carried out within the framework of the technology under consideration are designed to confirm or refute this statement.

The profiling system only allows one to make an assumption about the possible involvement of a passenger in an act of unlawful interference. The real threat can be revealed only based on an in-depth personal search of the passenger and the things he is carrying.

The concepts of "profiling", "profiling" in applied psychology define technologies for identifying potentially dangerous people and situations, as well as technologies aimed at preventing illegal illegal actions.

Profiling is, first of all, methods and techniques that allow you to create a psychological wiper and establish the type of personality according to certain signs of behavior: emotions, speech, thinking style, gestures, facial expressions and appearance.

Profiling is currently widely used by law enforcement agencies, since a systematic analysis of crimes allows you to create a psychological profile of a person who harbors criminal plans and commits illegal actions.

Such a psychological profile is based on a description of the characteristic distinctive features of a person's appearance and behavior, that is, signs of illegal intent. A detailed analysis and description of these features makes it possible to identify and classify potentially dangerous citizens. Thus, profiling or typology of a person according to a certain profile (type) helps to identify a potential offender [6].

The methodological foundations of profiling are the studies of psychologists P. Ekman, V. Friesen, K. Scherer, M. Zuckerman, V.A. Labunskaya and O. Fraya.

The main content of profiling, in the context of its application by officials of the customs authorities, is the organization and implementation of a set of socio-psychological measures, which are reduced to:

- firstly, to express diagnostics (2-3 minutes) of personal characteristics (psychological profile) of a person crossing the customs border, based on the analytical method of determining the negative signs of a person's verbal and non-verbal behavior, describing the appearance potential offender and forecast of his behavioral tendencies;

- secondly, to predict scenarios for the development of situations and actions of a particular person, models of his behavior and possible ways of communication.

In the conditions of professional activity of the DLTO, the main task of profiling is the prevention of illegal actions as a result of identifying potential offenders in the implementation of customs control based on the use of applied methods of psychology.

It is important to note that profiling technologies work quickly, simply and reliably, since everything you need to know about a person is reflected in his behavior, speech and gestures. The profiler only needs to know what to pay attention to. The use of profiling technologies in the professional activities of the DLTO allows you to quickly assess the emotional state, features of cognitive processes and the interlocutor's ideas about himself and the world.

Profiling improves the performance of the DLTO's duties. In this regard, it should be noted that at the Customs Institute of the Republic of Uzbekistan, additional professional programs have been developed and are being implemented to master the methods of profiling for students. The implementation of such programs is aimed at improving the professional competencies of DLTOs, improving the quality of their professional activities within the framework of their functional duties.

As noted above, an important component of profiling is express diagnostics, the use of which makes it possible to identify potentially dangerous citizens by social characteristics and psychological characteristics. A significant advantage of express diagnostics is that it can be carried out as soon as possible, without attracting the attention of others and using technically sophisticated equipment. Express diagnostics for profiling persons crossing the border can be carried out by a specially trained customs inspector.

Express diagnostics consists of four components:

1. Observation of appearance, verbal and non-verbal behavior.
2. Communication using survey technologies.
3. Emotional profiling.
4. Determination of a psychological profile (reading of psychotypes, identification of archetypes, definition of metaprograms).

A psychotype is a complex of mental characteristics that make up a generalized model of a person's behavior and his reactions to external stimuli.

Observation by the customs inspector of the appearance, verbal and non-verbal behavior of a person allows you to create a general idea of him as a dangerous or non-dangerous person crossing the border.

The appearance of a person, which includes clothes, accessories, hairstyle, can tell a profiler a lot [7].

For example, if a person has flown in from Turkey, is dressed in military style, has Islamic accessories, has a short haircut, wears a beard, then perhaps this is a terrorist who is moving from Syria.

An important indicator in determining illegal intentions is the verbal and non-verbal behavior of a person. When observing a person crossing the border, the customs inspector, as part of the analysis of verbal signs, should pay attention to the timbre and tone of voice, speech speed, pauses, reservations, speech errors, various tricks to directly posed test questions, and within the framework of non-verbal signs - on postures, gestures and facial expressions [8].

Verbal signs reveal a lie, since it serves as a means of presenting a behavior model. If a person is lying, then at the verbal level it will look like silence (refusal to talk, translation of the topic of conversation) and speech distortion (intentional distortion of the picture of events). The desire to discuss details, assessments and condemnations in the context of the conversation, accompanying the speech with emotional experience (empathy, anger) can serve as messages for truthful speech [9].

Detection of lies by non-verbal signs is associated with the analysis of postures, gestures and facial expressions of a person, which a customs inspector should pay attention to when determining, evaluating and predicting illegal actions of potentially dangerous persons crossing the customs border. It is important to note that the main information about a person's behavioral tendencies in profiling is taken from the analysis of non-verbal signs [10].

To identify persons with illegal intentions in profiling (express diagnostics) carried out by officials of the customs authorities, polling technologies are widely used. Thus, the Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan knows a special technique for interviewing passengers, the essence of which is to build an appropriate algorithm and rules for asking questions: relevant, control, symptomatic and neutral:

- an appropriate question is asked to identify a psychological reaction and the accompanying physical manifestation (for example, "Are you smuggling?");
- the control question aims to identify a false answer and signs of a person's behavior with a false answer in order to compare similarities and differences in response (for example, "Have you ever had to lie in a conversation with officials?");
- a symptomatic question is used to establish whether it causes a tense reaction in a person crossing the customs border, a conversation on extraneous topics (for example, "Did something happen to you?");
- a neutral question must be really neutral. It is asked to camouflage pertinent questions (for example, "Did you like the city you visited?").

Emotional profiling is an integral part of express diagnostics. It is carried out in order to determine the emotions and emotional reactions that affect a person. Emotions are mental processes that reflect the inner world of a person, therefore, by correctly determining the emotional reaction of a person crossing the customs border, one can determine his behavioral tendencies. The profiler should pay attention to such emotions as surprise, interest, joy, embarrassment, sadness, anger, shame, disgust, contempt, fear, curiosity, confidence [11].

The definition of a psychological profile based on the reading of psychotypes and the definition of metaprograms is the final analytical part of express diagnostics. Metaprograms determine the personal characteristics of a person, his values, perception and behavior. In profiling, the following psychotypes are distinguished:

- psychopathic,
- narcissistic
- schizoid,
- paranoid,
- depressive
- manic,
- masochistic

- obsessive-compulsive
- hysterical,
- dissociative (antisocial) [12].

The last stage of psychological profiling is the definition of metaprograms or ways of thinking of a person. The definition of metaprograms allows you to determine the psychological profile of a person according to the rules, algorithms and use of information”, “the level of generalization and specification of information”, “place (area) of attention”, “perception style” and others [13].

The concept of profiling is based on the fact that an illegal act and its preparation can be detected by analyzing a certain set of physical, psychological, behavioral signs that characterize suspects from the standpoint of their potential danger.

There are indicators that are critical for classifying a person as a risk group (demonstrated aggression, hidden aggression, agitation, detachment). The emotional state of a person, which is assessed by signs of anxiety, fear, excitement, etc., is considered in profiling as an additional factor in the analysis of the identified dominant signs.

There are key signs in the non-verbal and verbal behavior of a person that allow profilers to identify him in the human stream and classify him as potentially dangerous.

It is important to note that when conducting express diagnostics and formulating profiling results, all indicators must be taken into account. Thus, the analysis of the features of the use of profiling technologies in the professional activities of the DLTO and the description of some applied methods and profiling techniques to identify potentially dangerous persons crossing the customs border allow us to draw certain conclusions:

- firstly, the use of profiling technologies in the professional activities of the DLTO contributes to the prevention of illegal actions in the process of identifying negative signs of verbal and non-verbal human behavior in an analytical way, describing the appearance of a potential offender and predicting his behavioral tendencies;

- secondly, profiling is a system of theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as a set of effective psychological technologies, the use of which determines the conduct of express diagnostics to identify potentially dangerous persons, followed by an assessment of the situation and the choice of ways to prevent illegal actions;

- thirdly, training in profiling in the system of customs professional training is aimed at improving the professional competencies of officials necessary to solve the main task facing the Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan - the suppression of illegally moved objects across the customs border.

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